

CAPTURING SILENCES OF SPEAKING ARCHIVES: THE 'HAERENGA' OF INDIA'S AUDIOVISUAL PRESERVATION ECOSYSTEM

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Abstract - The founder of a private Indian cinema and cinema related material archive, The Cinema Resource Centre (TCRC) in the South Indian city of Chennai wonders how she should keep safe the collection of film material she has pieced together. What is taking 'good care' of such archives/collections? The straightforward answer might be applying preservation techniques, investing in archival skills and digitization, which the centre is trying to cope with. But 'good care' can also be interpreted as mobilizing the archives and creating public outreach and engagement programming, where the static material would start to speak.

By deep diving into the workings of four private Indian film related material archives and collections namely TCRC, MaNaSu Foundation, Archive of Indian Music and Raymond Israel's private collection, this paper aims to understand their challenges, how they navigate them and how they hope to harness the creative potential of their holdings for the future. These experiences can help facilitate knowledge exchange between private archivists and the research community, education and civic society practitioners as well as policymakers in order to enhance the development of effective strategies that raise awareness in digitization of archival practices.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The posters, backed by hardboard and protected by thick, clear plastic sheets are stacked

neatly on custom-made improvisations of baggage trolleys. This arrangement makes it easy to flip through the collection of 300 film posters that Zimra's late husband, Raymond Israel had ardently collected over the course of 20 odd years. She also has boxes of film memorabilia like old tickets, film magazines and pamphlets that await sorting. However, these precious items that hark back to a bygone era are in need of safe homes where the collection and items can go. Zimra, who is inching towards an advanced age, was most enthused when told about the idea of digitizing the entire collection. This would mean that Raymond's life's collection remained intact in the digital space, even if the materials eventually dispersed. Though certainly not an archive, this small collection of posters and film material aspires to be one. It even has the potential and inclinations, lest the collector gets help from institutions in cataloguing and digitizing it. Such collections of materials bring home the fact that these ephemera are in peril unless transferred to digital formats, and face a serious danger of being lost to oblivion without policy frameworks, expertise and funding that aids private collectors.

Challenges are galore for private but passionate archivists - training staff in the digitization process, resources crunch, struggle for a dedicated archival space for the archive, the indifferent attitude towards archiving, lack of institutional support and grants and limited scope for knowledge sharing. These archivists oftentimes devise their own means and practices to achieve their objectives of creating

cultural awareness and empathy in the public for the treasure they are the keepers of.

What are the lessons that can be drawn from the practices of private film related material archives and collections and the various challenges that they face with digitization becoming the mainstay of archives. Apart from this, how are they ensuring that they do not lose sight of public engagement programs in order for their collections to be relevant and elicit interest? How is digitization helping them in the process and to harness their creative potential for the future are some of the questions that we seek answers to by examining these private bodies.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

When we think of an archive, its materiality is taken for granted. That it will be a place where one finds reams of old papers, documents and bric-a-brac. In short it is assumed to be a physical thing with tangible dimensions. Scholars such as Ann Laura Stoler [1] and Achille Mbembe [2] suggests that the physical qualities of film, tape or paper shape the meaning of archive as much as the content it carries. For private archivists, the deterioration of material like cellulose reels, magnetic tapes, or fading newsprint threatens both memory and history. Their engagement is therefore deeply tactile like collecting, repairing and cataloguing which reminds us that preservation is a struggle with material fragility as much as with institutional invisibility.

However one cannot ignore the digital realm that is into our lives and technological developments that have changed the archives as we know them. As Derrida reminds us in *Archive Fever* [3], the archive is not merely a physical collection but a site of power and desire that governs what should be remembered and what is to be forgotten. In the field of film studies, archivists, collectors and archivists are faced with an array of new challenges with the digital turn when it comes to creating copies and preservation. These are issues relating to “digitization to questions over artistic appropriation and scholarly reinterpretation of archival material and is forcing them to develop new paradigms, methodologies and alternative ways of thinking to respond to them.” [4] This broader understanding is essential when thinking

about private collectors in India, whose holdings exist outside official infrastructures and challenge the monopoly of institutional archives.

While researchers are interested in the contents of archival documents and the messages that the ephemera are communicating, it is the collectors and archivists who are concerned with the physicality of the record. The material properties of things like the quality of the various kinds of papers, cloth, wood, film, magnetic tape, image negatives etc assume great importance. Damage or loss of the material means that its message is lost forever. Therefore meaning making for a researcher and an archivist or collector differs here. This process begins from the technicalities of collecting, documenting, preserving, and, despite all odds, showcasing it to the people who constantly engage with them on a regular basis. [5] Also the act of preservation here is not only technical but aspirational, embedding hope that these materials will find recognition and circulation. Arjun Appadurai describes archives in postcolonial contexts in his work “Archives of aspiration,” [6] where communities and individuals construct repositories as acts of cultural survival and self-representation.

It is evident in the work of Smith Rumsey [7] who warns of the precarity of digital memory, where the access, format obsolescence and ownership of archives raise new challenges. For private collectors with limited resources, digitization is not simply a preservation strategy but the beginning of digital *haerenga* or journey.

Elucidating the all-encompassing definition of a film archive to include cinema materials other than film – “It involves the tracing of the wider imprint of cinema, composed of a differentiated, multiple and intermedial dynamic.” [8] Film and media scholar Ravi Vasudevan further elaborates how cinema leaves its trace in other media that sets off interesting interactions. Thus, this paper situates private Indian archivists within a theoretical terrain that spans power (Derrida, Mbembe), aspiration (Appadurai), materiality (Stoler), digital precarity (Smith Rumsey), and intermediality (Vasudevan). These frameworks not only posit the challenges but also offer possibilities of sustaining fragile, overlooked collections from material survival to digital presence. Studying the workings of four small private collectors of cinema related materials in

India with this framework in view helps unravel their journeys so far that can inform a more resilient digital future.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

We use the case studies method to present four private film related material collections and archives. These are - The Cinema Resource Centre, Chennai; MaNaSu Foundation, Bengaluru; Archive of Indian Music, Bengaluru; Raymond and Zimra Israel, Pune/ Mumbai. The founders have been interviewed by way of a semi-structured interview. The four private bodies have been analyzed under the following five themes to understand their practice in detail and draw learnings - About the archive, Nature of the Collection and Inspiration; Collecting and Archiving Experiences; Challenges with Digitization; Other Challenges; Community Engagement and Archive Activation Programs.

Private collectors with film related materials operate and strive to expand, document and digitize their collections despite significant challenges. Their existence is as essential to the archival ecosystem as are the various established, state-run film archives. They safeguard what would have otherwise been lost despite no monetary gains. Studying their processes and experiences offer revealing insights into the practical aspects of running, funding, digitizing and activating public engagement of the archival collection of serious private collectors.

IV. CASE STUDIES

A. *The Cinema Resource Centre (TCRC), Chennai*

1. *Nature of the Collection and Inspiration*

TCRC is a not-for-profit public archive of Indian cinema that enables research on the visual and audio-visual cultural artifacts produced by Indian films, especially those in regional languages of South India. [9] They seek to promote film culture from a historical, educational, and artistic perspective.

According to its founder, Sruti Harihar Subramanian, the idea of TCRC slowly started to grow with her being curious about films. She thus started picking up and stowing away cut outs of film articles in magazines, movie tickets and later on salvaging heaps of materials like continuity photo

albums, lobby cards, posters. From being a film aficionado, Sruti eventually took up the profession of a filmmaker.

2. *Collecting and Archiving Experiences*

When her personal collection became too large and with the realization that there existed a gap between the industry and the audience, she decided that an archive was the need of the hour. Sruti's sources were film studios and offices that were junking film related material, and also scrap dealers. For TCRC the collection stops at born digital items. With a focus on taking care of what they presently have, they are not actively seeking to acquire more materials. As the centre shifted locations for want of space or other reasons, the collection followed as well. In order to start the archiving process Sruti hired Prasad to organize and digitize the smaller paper items like magazines.

3. *Challenges with Digitization*

Regarding preservation of films, she has invested in a Linear Tape-Open (LTO) technology for her film *Far Afternoon* that won the prestigious National Award. However, keeping up with the changing versions of LTOs is unaffordable for even one film, let alone her entire collection. Where she was not the film producer, she could just suggest an LTO version which was shelved due to budget constraints. Also, with no control on the resolution of film promotional material, she is left with low resolution images that were put out on social media. With raw footage of all her films and even the digitized paper material of the centre stored on hard disks, there is a risk of losing data to technical issues. The TCRC archivist, Prasad follows a 1 plus 1 rule, with both hard disks in different geographical locations. He has tried to upload the data on the cloud but without success, so the centre uses hard disks. In her own words, "we are so bootstrapped" Sruti says to describe the archive's precarious financial situation that restricts their digitization functions. Also, the centre has managed to digitize only 20% of their collection due to a manpower crunch.

4. *Other Challenges*

TCRC struggles with questions of how to present film related materials. For example, in the case of velvet albums of continuity photos of film sets that

the centre rescued, the centre wonders if the photos should be digitized and kept back in the album or catalogued and archived separately. As a film material, will the photos kept in the album best tell the story, as even the stains on the album are evocative, though this is not the right archival way? Another challenge is having enough dedicated space for community building activities as well as for archiving and digitization, along with necessary storage solutions for the materials. Acquiring skills for archiving and digitizing work is another challenge with limited funds and opportunities for conservation of film related materials. Sruti has said that having people skilled in library sciences and grant writing would also be an advantage to TCRC. So it comes down to space, money, human resources and skill; hurdles that small private collectors need to overcome to serve the cause of archiving better.

5. *Community Engagement & Archive Activation Programs*

TCRC is intent on being more than an archive and that's they why call themselves a resource center, according to the founder. Presently they are open by appointment to researchers and visitors. However their larger aspiration is to be like a museum with film and archiving themed activities like screenings, exhibitions and discussions. But without a dedicated space, these community building plans are on hold. The center recently collaborated with the India Foundation for the Arts (IFA) and ran a program, inviting researchers to engage with their archive collection of lobby cards and Tamil cinema reviews in periodical publications. With the selected applicants having to visit and research the collections at the TCRC premises, this was a meaningful community engagement exercise for the centre.

B. *Mannam Narasimhan Subbamma (MaNaSu) Foundation, Bengaluru*

1. *Nature of the Collection and Inspiration*

MaNaSu Foundation based in Bengaluru in South India, primarily works towards compilation and publication of complete works of well-known Telugu language authors. It was established towards the end of 2006 by three brothers Mannam Venkata Rayudu, Dr Gopichand Mannam and Dr

Mannam Chandra Mouli. It was while working on the works of one of the first Telugu film lyricist, that foundation had to seek out and document film-related materials like song books and gramophone records to trace the right song writers and newspaper archives for film advertisements and credits. While collectors let them access their material, they would ask for them to be returned.

2. *Collecting and Archiving Experiences*

Thus started their scanning and digitization of all literature related to Telugu language. E-Chitrapuri (loosely translated as Electronic- world of images) was the foundation's project that dealt with the collection and digitization of any material available on Telugu cinema. That included 78 rpm gramophone records, negatives of working stills, movie magazines, reviews and cinema advertisements in newspapers and preservation of films in public domain. This project has significantly contributed archival photos to coffee table books on three popular Telugu film actors. MaNaSu Foundation has also been instrumental in contributing majority of the available material on Telugu films on Indiaincine.ma, which is an annotated online archive of Indian film intended to serve as a shared resource for film scholars and enthusiasts in India and beyond. [10]

The centre runs a community archiving and scanning centre in rural Andhra Pradesh. Here mostly female staff from nearby villages is trained to sort, index, page check, scan, do a quality check for missing material and rebind the book or magazine before sending it back to the collector. The centre has 23 computers, 7 duplex scanners and a few flatbed scanners of A3 size. Their cutting machines have been improvised by the staff to suit their specific needs. The foundation has some cloud space – 8 TB and hard disks of 9 TB. Venkata Rayudu calls it a scanning facility since digitization involves Unicode. All the scanned material is stored on hard disks that are with the foundation heads in 3 different locations. Whenever researchers request material they are given Google drive links to the specific files or data is shared via Internet-based computer file transfer services like We Transfer.

3. *Challenges with Digitization*

Eventually, the foundation started scanning any and all books in Telugu they could gain access to, but are struggling with OCR improvement for text

conversion after scanning. Venkata Rayudu envisages the use of AI to create audiobooks using voices of famous Telugu film personalities, as they have enough data to for machine training. Further he has said that application of digitized archival material for meaningful activation of the archives is a challenge. This is because there is limited technical wherewithal with external agencies especially when it comes to Telugu.

4. *Other Challenges*

A challenge the foundation faces is a decreased proficiency in Telugu among the local staff, so all the indexes prepared by them has to be scrutinized by Venkata Rayudu or someone equally competent to avoid mistakes in spellings and other errors. Another issue he faces while interacting with researchers is a lack of a thorough study of materials pertinent to their area of focus. Instead they expect material to be handed out to them by the foundation on a platter since it is all scanned anyway. The MaNaSu foundation prefers to cut down their scope of work and encourages researchers to do their homework so they know the specific titles they require.

5. *Community Engagement & Archive Activation Programs*

The foundation has an annual get-together for all those associated with MaNaSu and family members, totaling about 150, at its scanning facility. There are informal discussions at the meet on a range of subjects. The foundation is open to sharing all its material that is out of copyright with the public. According to Venkata Rayudu, this was the very objective of starting the foundation and they intend to start a dedicated website soon towards the fruition of this purpose. MaNaSu foundation has a website called Kathanalyam set up through collaborations that has about Telugu short stories 75,000 stories in PDF format.

C. *Archive of Indian Music (AIM), Bengaluru*

1. *Nature of the Collection and Inspiration*

Yesteryears Indian classical singer Gauhar Jaan's intriguing life and hugely successful career have been chronicled by historian and musician Vikram Sampath in his book "My Name is Gauhar Jaan: The

Life and Times of a Musician." Sampath's deep dive into the singer's world also piqued his interest in music production and consumption in the early decades of 20th century India. Further research revealed that India has no semblance of a state-run sound archive. Music as well as voice recordings were languishing in scrap markets or with reluctant-to-share private collectors. The dismal state prompted him to establish the Archive of Indian Music (AIM) in 2011. Sampath put to use historical context, his knowledge of sound digitization and conservation of sound materials acquired from a fellowship at Berlin and research at sound archives across Europe, in order to shape the archive.

2. *Collecting and Archiving Experiences*

The archive has about 15,000 records in its collection as well as an open access digital repository on a music streaming and sharing platform called Sound Cloud. The digitized audios include Indian music genres like Carnatic, Hindustani and folk music, theater recordings in various languages, voices of leaders like M K Gandhi, Rabindranath Tagore, Subhash Chandra Bose and cinema recordings in Hindi, Tamil and Telugu languages. Digitization is a slow process with only a part time staff and limited archival space. AIM has been able to digitize only about half of their records collection, and have not even started on other formats like audio cassettes. To steer clear of copyright issues Sampath refrains from putting out digital audio copies of works of famous singers on Sound Cloud till it is in copyright. The archive has created metadata for each sound material that corresponds with the digital version. With his extensive experience in working with archives, Sampath follows international metadata standards for organizing and quick retrieval of material.

3. *Challenges with Digitization*

Though AIM has a network of scrap dealers and donors, individual and institutional collectors are extremely reluctant to part with their holdings for digitization, fearing misuse. They do not realize that the listenership for such material is low anyway and digitization would save them from obscurity. Sampath has lamented that the collectors would rather let the records be destroyed than share them. Another issue with donated digitized material is that sometimes it is cleaned up extensively by inexperienced collectors using software, which makes the voice sound metallic. So it's a tough art,

according to Sampath, and very little has to be cleaned in terms of background noise to be as close as possible to the original sound. With Sampath's other occupations, a full time archiving professional who carries out the digitization and engagement work systematically is what AIM needs at present.

4. Other Challenges

Sampath has observed that in western countries private archives are housed within universities and receive manpower and space support. In India, archivists like him have to depend on the largess of institutes, like AIM's present host is an international wellness centre. His larger idea for the archive was to partner with prominent institutions and the government to create a National Sound Archive of India that would be a repository for all types of sounds, like radio, speeches and not just music or film. He is concerned that the recordings of India's state owned radio broadcaster, All India Radio, are being destroyed and "nobody really cares a toss for these," he says.

5. Community Engagement & Archive Activation Programs

AIM has been involved in interesting community engagement activities. One of them is introducing the digitization process of audio archives to electronics and digital signal processing students. Apart from technical know-how, they also learned about the back story of the artist along with listening sessions. However, the flipside was when the patron of the project left the institute, AIM's initiative floundered. Other efforts were pan-India sound exhibitions called 'Voices of India' where a mobile phone application enabled the visitor to listen to the artist while reading about their lives. The archive also collaborated with Google Cultural Institute to curate thematic exhibitions where gramophone recordings were curated for special occasions like patriotic recordings on Indian Independence day and pioneering women musicians on Women's day.

With grants hard to come by as a private archive Sampath has merged AIM under a body that he has established called Foundation for Indian Historical and Cultural (FIHCR). Apart from harnessing the power of storytelling through an interactive website to engage people with sound archives, he hopes the focus on history and conservation can make grants

that much easier to secure. He then plans to internally divert funds towards scaling up of the archive as they are in need of, in Sampath's words, "more money, manpower, and support."

D. Raymond and Zimra Israel's Collection, Pune/ Mumbai

1. Nature of the Collection and Inspiration

Raymond Israel was inspired by Hindi film posters that adorned the restaurant he visited when he was in the USA in 1994 and decided to start a collection of his own. With his Jewish Indian family being film enthusiasts, Raymond as a child would regularly visit cinemas in Bombay (now renamed Mumbai), the home of the Hindi film industry and in the city of Pune where the family lived.

2. Collecting and Archiving Experiences

Raymond would look to adding to his poster collection every time, he and his wife Zimra would come to India. Scrap markets, bazaars and individual collectors were his sources. Eventually the couple moved back to India in 2012 and started working on preserving the poster collection. They researched methods on their own and backed up the posters on hard cardboards. To preserve the poster paper they did not use adhesives. And to protect the cardboard backed posters, they covered the front with a plastic sheet, securing it with clear tape at the back. These are all stacked on custom make baggage trolleys in the couple's Pune home. However, the collection is not catalogued so there is no record of details like year of acquisition, or size, material etc. Raymond also has a film magazine and memorabilia collection that has not been sorted yet.

3. Challenges with Digitization

When asked about any efforts on their part to digitize the poster collection before it is dispersed, Zimra said that they were not "computer people" and that the thought never occurred to them. She acknowledged it as a good idea, though expressing concern over digitization costs, technical requirements like large scanners and manpower. She as a co-collector was oblivious to digitization grants offered by foreign institutes and confessed to never "bothering with such things." Zimra readily took up the offer of cataloguing the collection by the researchers of this paper. This would mean that

she would at least have a document listing the description of the items and prove handy when giving off the collection and drafting legal papers. She and her husband were averse to handing the items to the state film archive as Raymond had first hand experienced their apathy when it came to preservation of film related materials.

Though eager to share the poster collection and allow public access she was unaware that digitization and creating an online archive would help researchers in an effective manner, rather than only concentrating on the physical collection.

4. Other Challenges

Now with Raymond passing away and Zimra also being of advanced age, she wishes to divide and hand over the collection to various responsible institutions who would credit her husband and take care of the collection. She is firm about signing a MoU stipulating that a write-up and photo of Raymond should accompany the exhibits and that the institute would not be permitted to sell the posters at any point in time.

5. Community Engagement & Archive Activation Programs

In 2017, the couple organized an exhibition of the film posters to raise funds for a medical cause through their Rotary Club in Pune city. Zimra recounts that Raymond thought the collection must be shown to people else it would disappear without any public engagement. They were able to display 200 posters which were visited by around 150 people with a public talk by Raymond about his collection journey.

V. DISCUSSION AND ANALYSES

All the four film material collectors have not started out consciously on their current paths but were inspired along the way to start a collection in order to preserve a piece film heritage. Over time they became

keepers and then archivists of film materials. They as well could be “accidental archivists” using the term used by Nigerian filmmaker Didi Cheeka to describe his transformation to a preserver of the country’s post-independence celluloid heritage. We see from the experiences with their materials, that with similar frequency these accidental archivists have already been, or have become, activists for the cause of the films and repositories that ended up in

their custodianship by chance. [10] This activism can be seen extending to keeping the archive alive by investing time, manpower and funds in turning the material to digital and understanding the need for reaching audiences through digital methods. TCRC, AIM and MaNaSu Foundation’s fervent digitization efforts and Zimra Israel’s readiness to go that path aptly are illustrative of this archival activism.

With archives going digital, and changes in technology, the nature of the film material related archive is changing constantly as it starts a new life in the cloud or the hard disk as bits. We also see that the digitization exercise is what is determining the archive activity more than the conversations with the material and publics. This is echoed in Derrida’s words “The archiving produces as much as it records the event.” [3] This is particularly telling of MaNaSu Foundation’s community scanning facility that has created an ecosystem of its own and even with AIM’s various immersive and well thought out community engagement programs. Raymond and Zimra’s poster exhibition could also be an example, with the event proceedings being digitally recorded.

All the four collections recorded here have been focusing on scanning their paper and sound based materials into digital content, for ease of access to the public and researchers and also as a method of preservation as the original items face deterioration. While scholars like Abby Smith, way back in 1999 had said that “digitization is not preservation- at least not yet”, [11] eventually there has been a consensus that digitization assists traditional preservation and conservation efforts by expanding access and reducing the handling of fragile originals. This resonates with the processes of the three archives. With TCRC, they started with smaller materials and struggle with questions of correct archival methods of preservations. AIM is interested in digital sound so that there are digital copies even if the sound material gets damaged and MaNaSu Foundation mostly returns materials that come to them for digitizing and has a small material collection. Zimra Israel who has not had a digital experience however sees value in the exercise. All the four collections face some challenges on the digitization front like application of digitized archival material for meaningful activation of the archives, technical wherewithal regarding Indian languages, digital obsolescence and availability of trained

manpower. Despite these hurdles we see them practicing their own versions of digitization as preservation strategies to safeguard their material collections.

Digitization has alleviated some of the tension between the desire to provide access and the need to protect originals. [12] Since the discussion is about film related materials, access to them is valid issue. We see that the archives are intent on keeping access to originals very controlled, with only Raymond's collection being exclusively material but out of reach of researchers.

An important theme observed are the plans in place for future preservation and continued engagement of digitized content with the community. TCRC dreams to be the resource centre that it set out to be, more than an archive and almost like a museum where activities like screenings, discussions, exhibitions and conferences would take place. Apart from focusing on storytelling through an interactive website to engage people with sound archives, Sampath of AIM is taking care that grants can be sought easily. MaNaSu Foundation's comfortable self-financed situation makes it easier for them to activate their digitized content through publications and Zimra is keenly looking for responsible homes for her husband's poster collection.

VI. CONCLUSION

So far we have zoomed in our lens at the micro level where private film archives operate. Changing the focus look at the macro level will help gauge the larger Indian audio-visual archiving context within which they are placed. National Film Archive of India (NFAI) has been the custodian of the country's film and non-film material since it was established in 1964. Its film preservation journey has been riddled with issues like storage vaults with faulty services, space crunch, fire that destroyed silent-era films, missing reels, lack of funds and weak archival strategies. Over the years the situation at the NFAI has improved. The National Film Heritage Mission (NFHM) launched in 2014 was intended to fast-track the preservation, digitization, and restoration of the country's cinematic heritage. By 2024 the project was at its halfway mark with more than 5600 films digitized and made available for public screenings. [13] The National Film Development Corporation (NFDC) was formed in 2020 after the merger of four public funded film units that includes the NFAI. [14]

The NFDC-NFAI has recently announced a project to conserve various film artifacts, including scripts, disc records, movie posters, lobby cards, costumes, newspaper clippings, film magazines, and equipment. Planned to start upon the completion of the NFHM in 2025, the project may also restore materials currently held by private individuals or institutions, such as prosthetics, costumes, and set models. While this move holds immense promise of mobilizing the rich repositories of private archives, a thrust on digitization strategies will further the cause of conserving these film materials. All India Radio (AIR) and Doordarshan (DD), India's national radio and television have also experienced poorly maintained audio-visual archives. In recent years, both media bodies have digitized their archival content and monetized it by releasing DVDs and CDs of their archival material and publishing it on social media. [15] Another development in 2014 was the National Cultural Audiovisual Archives (NCAA) project by the Ministry of Culture to digitize unpublished non-commercial audio and video recordings by partnering with cultural bodies. [16] This project had the potential to be a boon for small, private archives to work with the government to create a credible, central digital repository. However, data regarding the NCAA's impact on the cultural scenario is unavailable and plans to establish it as independent agency for outreach are obscure. Against this institutional history, the situation of the private film archive is shaky, with intermittent glimmers of governmental handholding.

Challenges are galore for private but passionate archivists - training staff in the digitization process, resources crunch, struggle for a dedicated archival space for the archive, the indifferent attitude towards archiving, lack of institutional support and grants and limited scope for knowledge sharing. Creating cultural awareness and empathy in the public for the treasure they are the keepers of is another significant difficulty for them. The lessons learnt from their successes and failures are important to note as they can dictate policy decisions for private cinema archives. Funding issues is a recurrent theme that needs to be addressed by deliberating on policy measures that can help create a viable archiving and digitization ecology. Tax incentives for small cultural institutions and their technical and other vendors is one such suggestion. Creating central or state level cultural

funding schemes can be a boost for smaller archives. Initiatives in India can be modeled on the lines of the National Endowment for the Humanities or the Institute of Museum and Library Services of the United States. These can be mandated to support smaller archives or individuals with tailored grants rather than concentrating on funding government institutions or established artists. Global grants are available for audiovisual and media archival projects but they require Indian institutions, especially nonprofits, to have Foreign Contribution Regulation Act 2010 (FCRA) clearances to apply. This severely restricts the scope for smaller archives who have limited resource to deal with long-winding financial procedures to secure international grants. Implementing a policy in favor of smaller archives so that are exempt from FCRA rules would open up a world of grant opportunities for them.

Activating digitized collections and creating avenues for public engagement for the archives to be relevant is another concern that crops up. Setting up co-curation projects with state cultural departments would provide sustainable pathways for long-term preservation while respecting the autonomy and curatorial role of private archivists. This would safeguard the agency of the private archivist while making the collection available for research or exhibition across institutions.

These are some innovative proposals stemming from the challenges that small, private archives encounter in their incredible journeys. However in the current landscape of limited institutional support it is often the innovative and consistent efforts of these archives that ensure continuity of preservation programs and systems when it comes to cinema material archiving and digitization.

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